

Surface properties of 2D nanoparticles

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1. Introduction

In the last decade, huge research efforts have been devoted to new types of nanomaterials, two-dimensional (2D) materials. 2D nanoparticles such as graphene, metal oxides and hydroxides, MoS₂ and the others are currently the most intensive studied materials that have great potential for future applications. The current intense interest in these materials is due to the unique properties resulting from their dimension. They offer highly specific surface areas as well as electronic structures that can achieve new interesting features. Graphene was the first 2D material isolated in 2004 [1] and extensively studied by many research teams.

MXenes are a new class of 2D inorganic materials, first described in 2011 [2]. Different MXenes are prepared from different MAX phases of the formula M_{n+1}AX_n, where M is the most common transition metal, A is an element of the 13 or 14 group of the periodic table of elements, X is usually C and/or N. By etching of the A layers from MAX phase, MXene are formed with the formula M_{n+1}X_nT_x where T is a functional group e.g., -O, -F, -OH. MAX phase. Number of papers about MXenes increases rapidly in last two years as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Numbers of papers about MXenes according Web of Science database (September 2019).

In this work ageing of 2D nanoplateforms, GO and MXene was study by their surface characterization using various methods, preferentially X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Stability of all materials is crucial for further application.

2. Materials and methods

Graphite (particle size 5 µm, SGL Carbon GmbH, Meitingen, Germany) was used for graphene oxide (GO) preparation. GO was obtained by a modified Hummers and Offeman method. The exfoliation was performed by numerous repetitions of mixing, sonication and Centrifugation. The prepared solution of GO was composed of 90 % GO monolayer particles, with a lateral size 302 ± 183 nm.

Ti₃AlC₂, particle size 40 µm (MRC, Ukraine) was used for MXene preparation by etching using LiF and HCl, followed by mixing and centrifugation.

The XPS measurements were performed using a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha XPS system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, UK) equipped with a microfocused monochromatic Al K X-ray source (1 486.6 eV).

3. Results and discussion

Graphite powder (G5) used for GO production was characterized first. G5 showed only slight oxidation with no other contaminants on its surface. G5 surface composition was 90.2 at. % C and 9.8 at.% O. GO showed some traces of surface contamination by sulfur, potassium and chloride from the reaction procedure, therefore GO was purified in the next step. XPS spectra of GO clearly demonstrates the formation of carbon-oxygen bonds (C–O at ca 287 eV, C = O at ca 288 eV and OC = O at ca 289 eV) on its surface. Chemical composition of GO detected by XPS was 70.8 at.% C, 28.2 at.% O, 0.2 at.% S and 0.1 at% N. Prepared GO was used for creation of hybrids for cancer detection by surface modification with magnetic nanoparticles and antibodies. Hence, stability of this 2D material was checked after few months and finally after 3 years after preparation, when stored in aqueous solution. Fig. 2 demonstrates C1s region of XPS spectra of fresh prepared GO and stored three years in aqueous suspension. Obtained results of XPS showed, no further oxidation of GO was detected.

Fig. 2. XPS of C1s region of GO spectra, fresh prepared and after three years storage in aqueous suspension.

XPS analysis confirmed etching the aluminium layer out of the Ti_3AlC_2 MAX phase. The intensity of Al signal decreased from 12.9 at.% to 0.0 at.% [4]. Results also showed cleaning MXene from oxidized parts, which are in precursor MAX phase in a larger amount. Oxidation of MXene was detected by XPS. Oxygen content increased and Ti content decreased after three weeks stored at ambient condition. When MXene was stored under argon atmosphere oxidation is slower.

4. Conclusions

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to confirm the structural and chemical composition of the prepared GO and MXene, and also for study of the surface composition during ageing of these 2D nanoplateforms. XPS confirmed that GO in solution is stable few years, no further oxidation of GO was detected.

Experimental condition of MAX phase etching and methods of MXene preparation significantly influence the final electrical conductivity of this 2D material. It is found that the high electrical conductivity and mobility of MXene can accelerate the charge transfer, what opened opportunities for the use of MXene as potential materials solar cell applications.

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